

“RESEARCH-BASED TRANSFORMATION OF TEACHER EDUCATION: TRADITION AS A BASIS FOR INNOVATION” International Conference on Teacher Education

THE DEVELOPMENT OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN FOREIGN LANGUAGES

Abdurahimova Nasiba,
Student of Uzbek State World Languages
University Group 2221
nasibaxonimabdurahimova@gmail.com

Supervisor:
Saydibragimova Yulduzxon

Abstract. This scientific paper investigates the complex process of becoming a proficient communicator in another language. In addition to linguistic proficiency, communicative competence also includes sociolinguistic and strategic competencies. It is an essential component of language learning. The research explores the theoretical bases of communicative competence and looks at the potential applications for language learners and teachers. In addition, several elements that impact the growth of communicative competence are covered, including motivation, exposure to real language use, and cultural awareness. The paper also identifies successful teaching methods and tactics that can help foreign language learners become more proficient communicators. The objective of this study is to enhance comprehension of the process by which people can develop proficiency in a second language by illuminating these crucial elements.

Keywords: communication, language learning, communicative competence, sociolinguistic competence, crucial skill, platforms.

Introduction

The development of communicative competence is a component of learning a foreign language, which goes beyond simply learning vocabulary and grammar rules. Effective language use in a variety of settings to accomplish communication objectives is referred to as communicative competence. The significance of communicative competence in learning a foreign language will be examined in this article, along with methods for fostering it.

Comprehending Communicative Competence (CC)

Cc includes discourse, linguistic, sociolinguistic, and strategic competencies. Grammar, syntax, and vocabulary are all part of linguistic competence. Sociolinguistic competence is the ability to comprehend social norms, cultural norms, and appropriate language use in various contexts. Effective and coherent idea organization in written or spoken language is a requirement for discourse competency. Finally, strategic competence is the capacity to make up for lapses in communication by using techniques like summarizing or requesting clarification.

Communication Skills

An essential component of effective communication in everyday life is communicative competence. Language learners can communicate effectively with

“RESEARCH-BASED TRANSFORMATION OF TEACHER EDUCATION: TRADITION AS A BASIS FOR INNOVATION”

International Conference on Teacher Education

native speakers, accurately express themselves, and negotiate meaning thanks to it. Communication breakdowns may result from language learners' inability to effectively communicate their ideas or understand those of others.

Techniques for Increasing Communication Proficiency

1. **Immersion:** One of the best strategies for gaining communicative competence is to fully immerse oneself in the target language and culture. Studying overseas, taking part in language exchange programs, or interacting with real media like books, music, and films can all be examples of this.

2. **Practice Speaking:** Developing communication skills requires a lot of speaking practice. It is recommended that language learners converse with native speakers, take part in group discussions, and practice speaking in scenarios that mimic authentic communication scenarios.

3. **Emphasis on Functional Language:** Acquiring knowledge of language useful for routine communication tasks, like greeting people, requesting directions, or placing an order at a restaurant, can improve one's ability to communicate.

4. **Improve Your Listening Skills:** An essential part of communicative competence is listening comprehension. To get better at understanding spoken language, language learners should listen to a range of content, including podcasts, news broadcasts, and conversations.

5. **Utilize Technology:** Apps for learning languages, the internet, and online language exchange platforms can offer more chances to hone and expand your communicative skills.

Difficulties in Developing Communicative Competence:

Difficulties in developing communicative competence in a foreign language can be attributed to various factors, including cultural norm differences, fear of making mistakes, and limited opportunities for authentic communication. Pronunciation, intonation, and comprehension of colloquial expressions can also be problematic for language learners.

Conclusion

In summary, acquiring communicative competence in foreign languages is crucial for both successful language learning and efficient communication. Through an emphasis on linguistic, sociolinguistic, discourse, and strategic competencies, language learners can improve their capacity for confident and fluent real-world communication. Language learners can conquer obstacles and gradually increase their communicative competence through immersion, speaking practice, functional language learning, listening skill development, and the use of technology.

“RESEARCH-BASED TRANSFORMATION OF TEACHER EDUCATION: TRADITION AS A BASIS FOR INNOVATION”

International Conference on Teacher Education

References:

1. Iacuzzi, S., Garlatti, A., Fedele, P., & Lombrano, A. (2020). Integrated reporting and change: evidence from public universities. *Journal of Public Budgeting, Accounting & Financial Management*, 32(2), 291–310. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JPBAFM-08-2019-0120>
2. Manetti, G., Bellucci, M., & Oliva, S. (2021). Unpacking dialogic accounting: a systematic literature review and research agenda. *Accounting, Auditing & Accountability Journal*, 34(9), 250–283. <https://doi.org/10.1108/AAAJ-08-2020-4736>
3. Ian Macqueen. (2019). Testing transformation and decolonisation: Experiences of curriculum revision in a History honours module. *Yesterday and Today*, 22, 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.17159/2223-0386/2019/n22a1>
4. Kroeze, J. H. (2019). Is the philosophy of the Information Systems discipline informed by the arts and humanities? *Phronimon*, 20(1), 1–30. <https://doi.org/10.25159/2413-3086/4898>
5. Scott, K. C. (2021). A Review of Faculty Self-Assessment TPACK Instruments (January 2006 – March 2020). *International Journal of Information and Communication Technology Education (IJICTE)*, 17(2), 118–137. <https://doi.org/10.4018/IJICTE.2021040108>
6. Caffrey, C., Lee, H., Withorn, T., Clarke, M., Castañeda, A., Macomber, K., Jackson, K. M., Eslami, J., Haas, A., Philo, T., Galoozis, E., Vermeer, W., Andora, A., & Kohn, K. P. (2022). Library instruction and information literacy 2021. *Reference Services Review*, 50(3-4), 271–355. <https://doi.org/10.1108/RSR-09-2022-0035>
7. Brown, C. L., Ward, N., & Nam, B. H. (2019). “Only English Counts”: the impact of English hegemony on South-Korean athletes. *International Journal of Comparative Education and Development*, 21(3), 222–235. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCED-01-2019-0007>